

EVALUATION OF BEARING DAMAGE BEHAVIOR IN THIN TITANIUM FILMS-CFRP HYBRID LAMINATE

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1 Introduction

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) has been applied to aircraft and spacecraft because CFRP is light weight material compared to metal alloys. Application of CFRP enable us to manufacture large scale structure in the form of single-piece and considerable reduction of number of components has been achieved. Mechanical fastening using bolt-nut or rivets is one of the methods used for joining composite components for aircraft structure. Mechanical fastening is a well-known and well-established method and has the advantage in easy assembly or disassembly. However, composite laminates are sensitive to stress concentration around circular hole or notch, and this fact results in damage onset in low stress. For composite bolted joints currently applied to aerospace structures, thicker composite plates are used locally around the joints in order to achieve high strength for assuring the safety. This spoils the lightweight characteristics of carbon fibre composites. In this regard, composite bolted joints which have high specific strength and better robustness are required.

Applications of fiber metal laminates (FMLs) [1] with titanium alloy for composite bolted joints have been researched [2-4]. As for the material they examined, one can see the change of the main stress member as from the titanium layers into CFRP layer with the distance from the bolted joints. Furthermore, limited variation for the stacking sequences in hybrid region can be achieved because thickness of the titanium alloy sheets which is thicker compared to that of CFRP prepregs generally used.

In this paper, fiber metal laminates that consist of carbon fiber reinforced plastics and thin titanium films were applied to composite bolted joints to improve bearing damage behavior of composite laminates. Experimental evaluation is conducted to obtain better bearing damage behavior by inserting

thin titanium films. It should be noted that strength of the titanium films is not expected to contribute the bolted joints, but damage onset such as fibre kinking and shear cracking in the CFRP plies is suppressed by presence of the thin titanium films. With some results of bearing strength obtained by bolted joint tensile tests and bearing damage behavior in the hybrid laminates with various stacking sequences, optimization for the hybrid stacking sequence is discussed.

2 Experimental Procedure

2.1 Materials

Hybrid thin titanium-CFRP fiber metal laminates were assembled by laminating carbon fiber/epoxy prepregs (T700SC/2592, Toray) and pure titanium films (50 μ m, Sumitomo Metals Naoetsu Works), and they were cured in an autoclave. Since the hybrid laminates that consist of titanium and CFRP have attracted attention as a material that can withstand harsh environments such as high temperature, so titanium was selected in this study. Before the lamination, titanium films were soaked in hydrogen peroxide solution of 30% as surface treatment to improve their adhesion to epoxy resin [5]. Four types of the hybrid laminates were made by inserting five or eight titanium films into quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with stacking sequence of [45/0/-45/90]_{2S} as shown in Table 1.

2.2 Tensile tests for bolted joints

Bolted joint strength and bearing damage behavior in the laminates were investigated by tensile tests of bolted joints. Specimens were fastened by stainless bolts and nuts with diameter of 6mm with two cramping CFRP plates under clamping torque of 20 Nm. At the other side for the specimen, another CFRP plate was fastened as shown Fig.1. This unit

was mounted to tensile test machine by gripping each side. Tensile loading was applied to the specimen until ultimate failure under cross-head speed of 1.0 mm/min by Tensilon universal testing machine (RTF-1350, A&D) at room temperature. Bearing damages in the laminates after tensile tests were observed by digital optical microscope (VHX-1000,KEYENCE).

Table 1. Stacking sequence of specimens tested.

Specimen	Stacking sequence	Areal density [g/cm ²]
CFRP laminates	[45/0/-45/90] _{2S}	0.35
FML type A	[45/0/-45/Ti/90/45/0/Ti/-45/90/Ti/90/-45/Ti/0/45/90/Ti/-45/0/45]	0.46
FML type B	[45/Ti/0/Ti/-45/90/45/0/-45/90/Ti/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/Ti/0/Ti/45]	
FML type C	[45/0/-45/90/45/Ti/0/Ti/-45/90/Ti/90/-45/Ti/0/Ti/45/90/-45/0/45]	
FML type D	[45/Ti/0/Ti/-45/90] _{2S}	0.52

Fig.1 Geometry of specimen for bolted joint tests.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Load-displacement curves

Figure 2 shows bearing damage aspects of the specimens after the tensile test for bolted joints. For FML specimens one can see titanium films which were exposed by damage. In addition, for all specimens, one can see bearing fracture around circular hole portion along the direction of travel of the bolt. Therefore, in this test method, the net-tension fracture did not occur, only damage caused by bearing load due to bolt is generated in the laminate.

Figure 3 shows load-displacement curves of the quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates and four types of the hybrid laminates. Here displacement indicates that of the cross-head of the testing machine. Overall load values of the hybrid laminates were higher than that of the CFRP laminate because of the inserted titanium films. Displacement that indicates the maximum load of FML type A specimen shows smaller than the other FML specimens. There were load drop points in load-displacement curves, and they are considered to represent damage onset in the laminates.

Fig.2 Bearing damages in the specimens after the bolted joint tensile tests.

Fig.3 Load-displacement curves of tensile tests.

3.2 Bearing damage behavior in the quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates

One can see the first load drop point at 4.67 kN and damages in the CFRP plate were considered to initiate because the slope of the curve declined after this point. As the load value showed increase and decrease after the second load drop point of 10.7 kN, damage growth in this stage could be related to the load behavior.

Figure 4 shows the bearing damages in the CFRP plate around first load drop point. At 4.0kN, micro-buckling of the carbon fiber in 0° layer (in-plane fiber kinking) occurred first. After that, the out-of-plane fiber kinkings occurred and they induced matrix shear cracks in adjacent layers at first load drop point as shown in Fig.5. Matrix crackings which were induced by out-of-plane fiber kinkings after the first load drop were found to propagate through layers. Therefore, initial damages that occurred in the CFRP plates were in-plane fiber kinkings in inner 0° layers, however they did not affect the load drops. The occurrence of out-of-plane fiber kinking and the following damage propagation to the adjacent layers influenced on the load drops. Figure 6 shows that after the second load drop point at 10.7kN, damages were found to propagate through layers far from bearing region which bolt doesn't contact directly. In other words, the fibre kinking in 0° layer was the main factor that triggered the damage growth. Therefore, overall damage onset and propagation could be suppressed if the micro-buckling of the carbon fibres in 0° layer was somehow prevented.

Fig.4 Typical initial damage behavior observed in the CFRP laminate. (In-plane fiber kinking.)

Fig.5 Typical initial damage behavior observed in the CFRP laminate. (Out-of-plane fiber kinking.)

Fig.6 Bearing damages in the CFRP laminate after the second load drop.

3.3 Bearing damage behavior in the thin titanium-CFRP Fiber Metal Laminates

The first load drop points of the FML specimens were higher than that of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate. In particular, the FML type C specimen showed higher load compared to the other FML specimens. The first and second load drop points

were shown in Table 2. In Table 2 the normalized load denotes the peak load at the drop point normalized by the areal density of the specimen. As for the first load drop point superiority of the FML specimen is apparent especially for the FML type C specimen. However, the normalized loads using areal density for the FML specimen were comparable or lower than that of the CFRP laminates.

Figure 7 shows the bearing damages in the FML type A specimen around first load drop point. At 6.0kN, micro-buckling of the carbon fiber in 0° layer (in-plane fiber kinking) occurred first as well as the quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate. After that, the out-of-plane fiber kinkings occurred and they induced matrix shear cracks in adjacent layers at 7.0kN as shown in Fig.8. However, the load value of fiber kinkings and matrix cracks occurred in the FML type A specimen showed higher compared to the quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate. After the second load drop, at cross-sections near the bearing region for the FML type A specimen, the titanium films were found to prevent the matrix cracking to propagate into adjacent layer. This phenomenon was observed in initial stage for damage onset near the bolt (Fig.8), and also around the fibre kinking distant from the bolt with higher load as shown in Fig.9. Therefore, the titanium films inserted in CFRP laminates delayed damage onset in 0° layer and suppressed damage propagation into adjacent layers. As the result, overall damage showed low level compared to the quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate at the same value of tensile load.

Table 2. Load drop points in Load-Displacement curves.

(The peak load at the drop point normalized by the areal density and cross-section area of the specimen)

		CFRP	FML A	FML B	FML C	FML D
First load drop point	Load [kN]	4.67	6.87	7.09	7.37	7.09
	Normalized load [kNcm ² /g]	13.3	14.9	15.4	16.0	13.6
	Bearing stress [MPa]	216	289	302	314	285
Second load drop point	Load [kN]	4.67	6.87	7.09	7.37	7.09
	Normalized load [kNcm ² /g]	30.6	27.8	26.5	28.7	29.8
	Bearing stress [MPa]	496	539	520	562	623

Fig.7 In-plane fiber kinking in the FML type A specimen.

Fig.8 Out-of-plane fiber kinking in the FML type A specimen.

Fig.9 The titanium film prevents the matrix cracking to propagate into adjacent layers. (FML type A.)

Difference in bearing damage states in the FML specimens with different location of the titanium films were compared. For the FML type B specimen, the outer 0° layers were sandwiched by the titanium layers, and the damage growth induced by the fibre kinking was prevented, though damages induced by the out-of-plane fibre kinking in inner 0° layers were not suppressed (Fig.10). In contrast, one can see that overall damage for the FML type C specimen with the inner 0° layers sandwiched by the titanium films kept lower level especially at the first load drop point (Fig.11). It was observed that the titanium films prevented the fibre kinking-derived shear matrix cracking in internal region of the plate to propagate toward the surface. The titanium films which sandwiched all 0° layers in the FML type D specimen expected to suppress damage propagation from the 0° ply most among the four FML types of specimen, however this was found to be not the case as shown in Fig.12. Since the buckling in the titanium film itself possibly derives damages in CFRP plies, further evaluation for this matter should be required in order to achieve optimized hybrid stacking sequence.

Fig.10 Bearing damages in the FML type B specimen after the first and second load drop point.

Fig.12 Bearing damages in the FML type D specimen after the first and second load drop point.

Fig.11 Bearing damages in the FML type C specimen after the first and second load drop point.

It should be noted that damages in the composite plies are dominant in the FML specimen because the titanium films showed only plastic deformation without shear cracking. In particular, this phenomenon is remarkable when comparing the damage state of the same load at 10000N (Fig.13). Therefore the load drops in the load–displacement curves may be correspond to the damage onset and growth in the composite plies. Hence, one can understand that the normalized load at the second load drop were comparable between the CFRP and FML specimens since at that load level fibre kinking and matrix crashing occurred in every composite ply and plastic-deformed titanium films were not able to contribute to suppression of the damage in the composite plies and also the bearing load. On the other hand, initial damage onset and its growth were successfully suppressed by the titanium films as intended and resulted in the higher normalized load compared to the CFRP laminates as already shown in Table 2.

(a) Quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate.

(e) FML type D specimen.

(b) FML type A specimen.

(c) FML type B specimen.

(d) FML type C specimen.

Fig.13 Damages in the FML specimens under tensile loading of 10000N.

4 Conclusion

This paper introduced the fibre-metal laminates using thin titanium films to the composite bolted joints to improve joint strength and bearing damage behavior. Tensile tests for bolted joints in quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$ demonstrated that the first failure mode was the in-plane fibre kinking in 0° layers. And after that the out-of-plane fiber kinkings occurred and the matrix shear cracking in adjacent layers was induced by the kinking. As for the thin titanium films – CFRP hybrid laminates the matrix shear cracking was prevented from propagating into adjacent layers because of the titanium films. The overall damage level in the hybrid laminates was found to keep low when the titanium films sandwiched the inner 0° layers rather than outer. Stacking sequence which the titanium films sandwiched the inner 0° layers also resulted in damage onset in higher normalized load compared to the other FML specimens.

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